

TAKING PART IN RESEARCH: A GUIDE FOR CITIZEN SCIENTISTS ON ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE CONSIDERATIONS

Executive Summary

This guide is for citizen scientists taking part in research that may have environmental or climate implications, including projects linked to the European Green Deal¹. This means being actively involved in activities such as collecting data, interpreting results, or contributing to project decisions. This guide is designed to help you participate responsibly, understand how your contributions support environmental and climate knowledge and the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)² principle, and avoid actions that could unintentionally cause environmental or social harm.

At a glance, this guide helps you understand:

- Your rights as a citizen scientist, including receiving clear information, choosing whether to take part, and stopping your participation at any time
- Your responsibilities, such as following project instructions, acting honestly and carefully when collecting or sharing data, and respecting the environment and others involved
- How your participation can support research that is respectful to the environment and climate and contributes to positive outcomes for communities and ecosystems

For quick use, readers may start with the Checklist for Citizen Scientists and the Questions to Ask Yourself, which provide a simple way to reflect on participation and identify potential concerns, and then consult the relevant sections as needed.

Your contribution to research is valuable and should always take place in ways that are safe, transparent, respectful, and ethically sound. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences or where biosecurity considerations are relevant, additional safeguards and requirements may apply. The project team should explain these clearly before you decide whether to participate, and you should feel free to ask questions or seek clarification if anything is unclear.

Before you join: understand the project

1. Project purpose and who is behind it

You should receive a clear, short description of the project's aims (for example, monitoring local heat islands or tracking biodiversity change), who coordinates the project (institutions), who funds it, and how the results are expected to be used (e.g. informing local policies, contributing to scientific publications, supporting environmental management). This information should be provided in accessible, non-technical language. Where relevant, the project should also explain whether its activities or results could create environmental or social impacts beyond the immediate study context, including effects on other communities or future generations, and what measures are taken to minimise such risks.

2. Your role as a citizen scientist

The project should explain clearly what you will do, such as making observations, uploading photos or sensor data, joining workshops, or helping interpret results, including activities that may involve natural areas or environmental data.

¹The European Green Deal is the European Union's comprehensive growth strategy launched in 2019, aiming to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy. Its central goal is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, with an interim target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The framework covers energy, industry, agriculture, transport, and biodiversity to create a sustainable, inclusive, and clean, green transition.

²"Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) is a European Commission principle ensuring investments, particularly under the Recovery and Resilience Facility, do not cause significant environmental damage. It requires projects to meet criteria across six objectives, including climate change mitigation, adaptation, water protection, circular economy, pollution control, and biodiversity.

You are free to decide what level of involvement is realistic for you, and you are not obliged to take on tasks beyond what you agreed at the start. You can also adjust your level of involvement over time or decide to stop at any time.

3. What happens with the data you contribute

The project should explain which types of data will be collected including, where relevant, data that may be collected about you and data that you will collect or generate through your participation (for example dates, locations, measurements, photos, and any environmental or climate-related information you might gather). You should be informed on how to ask questions and feel comfortable asking them if anything is unclear. You should know where and for how long the data you will provide will be stored, how it will be protected and whether it will be openly available or shared under conditions. You should also know how you will receive feedback on results (e.g. maps, dashboards, newsletters or meetings). You should feel comfortable asking questions if anything is unclear.

4. Terms, conditions and duration

You should receive clear terms and conditions that explain how you can participate, how the data you contribute can be used, shared or reused, under which licence, and how long the project and its data infrastructure are expected to run. You should have an opportunity to read these and ask questions before you decide whether they are acceptable to you.

Your rights as a citizen scientist

1. Voluntary participation and right to withdraw

Participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to participate or withdraw at any time, without penalty. The project should tell you how to withdraw and what will happen to the data you have already contributed including community, environmental or climate-related data.

2. Informed consent

Before you start, you should receive a clear explanation of the project and your role, information on possible environmental benefits and risks, and a consent form (paper or digital) in understandable language. You should confirm consent only if you feel you understand what is involved. In some projects, especially in health and life sciences, additional institutional or regulatory approvals and safety rules may apply. These should also be explained.

3. Privacy and confidentiality

Privacy and confidentiality are especially important when research involves data that may indirectly reveal information about you, such as location data, observations linked to specific places, or contributions associated with identifiable individuals. This may be particularly relevant when datasets include sensitive environmental information (for example, endangered species locations, community sites, or places associated with participants).

4. Recognition and feedback

Your contribution should be acknowledged appropriately (for example in project reports, websites, or publications). You should be able to choose whether to be named or remain anonymous. The project should share results in accessible formats, such as summaries, visuals or public events, and explain how you and other participants contributed to the research (e.g., how your contributions helped advance environmental or climate understanding).

5. Involvement in decisions

Where suitable, you may be invited to help shape decisions about how data are collected and interpreted, how results are communicated, or how data are shared or reused. You are free to accept or decline these roles. Saying no should not affect your participation in the project.

6. Your knowledge, community data and benefit-sharing

If you provide local, environmental, cultural or traditional ecological knowledge to the project team, you have the right to ask how this knowledge will be used, stored and shared, whether your community or group will be recognised as a custodian of this knowledge, and what benefits are planned for you and your community if the research leads to applications or products.

You can decline to share knowledge that you or your community consider sensitive, sacred or vulnerable to misuse. Where knowledge is shared collectively, it may be important that consent and benefit-sharing are discussed at the community level, not only individually.

Your responsibilities as a citizen scientist

1. Act with honesty and care in data collection

Follow the project's instructions and protocols as closely as possible. You should not invent, alter, or selectively report observations. Inform the project team if you are unsure or may have made a mistake. These practices are an essential part of research integrity, which means producing trustworthy knowledge through honest and careful work.

Key integrity issues to keep in mind include fabrication (making up data), falsification (changing or omitting data to influence results), and selective reporting (only sharing results that support a preferred outcome). Noting uncertainties, limitations, or unexpected results is part of good research practice, especially when environmental or climate-related data may inform local decisions or policies.

You should also be aware that strong personal, professional, or community interests related to the research topic can unintentionally influence how data are collected or interpreted. Being open about such interests and following agreed protocols helps ensure that the research remains fair, credible, and useful to others.

2. Respect people's privacy

You should avoid capturing identifiable images or information about people (for example faces, license plates, house numbers) and avoid sharing other participants' personal information without consent. You should take care when posting project-related screenshots or maps on social media especially if they show sensitive environmental or location data.

3. Respect nature and local rules (Do No Significant Harm)

You should follow rules for protected areas and natural sites, including "[leave no trace](#)" principles, staying on marked paths where advised, avoiding disturbing wildlife (especially during breeding seasons), and following any biosecurity instructions such as cleaning boots to avoid spreading invasive species. You should also ensure your activities do not inadvertently block access to public spaces for others or create local nuisances (noise/light) while monitoring.

Non-personal environmental data (for example, animal behaviour, species presence, weather, water levels) should be gathered in the least intrusive way possible, avoiding disturbance, stress, injury or damage to animals and habitats. EU and national

rules on the ethical treatment of animals also apply when research is carried out by citizen scientists. If a protocol ever feels harmful or inappropriate for animals, you should stop and contact the project team for clarification.

You should not collect samples (such as plants, animals, soil) without explicit instructions and you should always respect local regulations and conservation rules. Take litter away and minimise your environmental footprint during field activities (e.g. choosing a sustainable mode of transport to reach sampling sites where possible).

4. Use technology responsibly

You should use only the official apps or tools provided by the project, keep your accounts and devices secure (for example, by using passwords and updates), and report technical problems such as GPS errors or app bugs to the project team. This is particularly important when your device collects location or environmental data that might be sensitive.

5. Support, inclusion and respect

You should treat other participants and community members with respect, welcome newcomers, and value different kinds of knowledge (local, Indigenous, expert, lay). Inclusive and respectful participation strengthens environmental and climate research and ensures diverse perspectives are represented. Report to the project team any harassment or discrimination you experience or observe.

6. Be open about your interests and roles

If you or your organisation have strong interests related to the project topic (for example employment in a company, NGO or public authority involved in the issue, or a role in a campaign or court case), you should tell the project team. This does not disqualify you from taking part; it helps avoid misunderstandings and supports fair interpretation of data especially when environmental or climate issues affect different groups differently.

Checklist for citizen scientists

Before joining

- I understand what the project is about and who is organising it.
- I know what my role will be and how often I am expected to contribute.
- I have read or received an explanation of how the data I will provide will be used, stored and shared.
- I have seen the terms and conditions and know how long the project is expected to run.
- I know how to ask questions and how to withdraw if I change my mind.
- I understand whether the project has environmental or climate implications and how my contribution supports fair and sustainable outcomes.
- I have been told how the project aims to avoid shifting environmental or social harms to other communities (including outside the EU) or future generations.
- I know I will receive a short introduction or training on collecting data, protecting privacy, and minimising environmental impacts.

While participating

- I follow the agreed protocols and ask for help when unsure.
- I respect privacy, nature and local rules.
- I record uncertainties or mistakes instead of hiding them.
- I use project tools responsibly and keep my account secure.
- If I feel unsafe or uncomfortable due to the behaviour of others, I know how to report this and trust that my concerns will be taken seriously.
- If I notice potential harm to nature or unintended impacts on certain groups, such as increased exposure to climate or environmental risks, I know how to raise this with the project team and expect them to respond promptly and transparently to my concerns.

After contributing

- I stay informed about how results and findings are communicated, including whether sensitive environmental or climate-related data are handled responsibly.
- I speak up if I see potential harm, misuse of data, or risks for communities or ecosystems.
- I make use of opportunities to learn from the results (e.g., meetings, dashboards, summaries) and understand how my contribution supports environmental or climate objectives.

Questions to ask yourself

- Do I feel free to say no or to stop participating if I want to?
- Do I trust the organisations running this project to use the data I contribute responsibly?
- Am I comfortable with how my personal data and location information are handled?
- Do I understand how my contribution can help address climate and environmental challenges?
- Is my participation respectful of nature, local communities, and my own wellbeing?
- If I am invited into decision-making (e.g. about data use or communication), do I feel that my voice is genuinely listened to?
- Does this project explain who benefits from the results and who might bear any environmental costs or risks, both locally and in other places that may be affected, including longer-term environmental or societal impacts?

If your answer to one or several of these questions is "no" or "not sure," consider discussing your concerns with the project team or seeking clarification before continuing your participation.

The consortium

